

SKIMMING AND SCANNING

Karimova Gozal Ikhtiyarovna

Associated teacher. Asian international university of teacher.

Narzullayeva Aziza

Student of international Asian University.

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***Abstract.** This scholarly work discusses the skillful use of SKIMMING and SCANNING to succeed in the reading portion of the IELTS exam. The topic of scientific work is interesting and attracts the attention of the scientific community.*

***Key words:** scanning, skimming, reading.*

ПРОСМОТР И СКАНИРОВАНИЕ

***Аннотация.** В этой научной работе обсуждается умелое использование беглого просмотра для успешной сдачи части экзамена IELTS по чтению. Тема научной работы интересна и привлекает внимание научного сообщества.*

***Ключевые слова:** сканирование, беглый просмотр, чтение.*

Ishning vazifasi; qisqa vaqt ichida butun matnni diqqat bilan o'qimasdan tekst mazmunini tushunish.

Ishning maqsadi; ushbu ilmiy ish maqsadi skimming va scanning o'rtasidagi farq va ularni chuqurroq tahlil qilish.

Tadqiqot usullari; tahlil qilish, tavfsiflash, solishtirish usullari.

Olingan natijalar va ularning yangiligi.

Reading is often treated as a technique. People read an article, book, etc, in order to gain some information or knowledge. Many times, one needs to read at a faster rate due to various reasons like lack of time, etc.

Skimming is a quick reading method, whereas **scanning** is a selective reading method. The main **difference** between **skimming and scanning** is that **skimming** tells you what information is contained in the section or in the document, while **scanning** helps you position a particular piece of information. The combination of **skimming and scanning** is even greater, as it allows you to read quicker without missing out Skimming and Scanning.

Skimming refers to the process of reading only main ideas within a passage to get an overall impression of the content of a reading.

selection.

How to Skim:

- * Read the title.
- * Read the introduction or the first paragraph.
- * Read the first sentence of every other paragraph.
- * Read any headings and sub-headings.
- * Notice any pictures, charts, or graphs.
- * Notice any italicized or boldface words or phrases.
- * Read the summary or last paragraph.

Scanning is a reading technique to be used when you want to find specific information quickly. In scanning you have a question in your mind and you read a passage only to find the answer, ignoring unrelated information.

How to Scan:

- * State the specific information you are looking for.
- * Try to anticipate how the answer will appear and what clues you might use to help you locate the answer. For example, if you were looking for a certain date, you would quickly read the paragraph looking only for numbers.
- * Use headings and any other aids that will help you identify which sections might contain the information you are looking for.

Reading, especially when done with a clear purpose of learning, requires a variety of strategies for a maximized effect on comprehension and information retention. To achieve your maximum potential, there are several strategies you absolutely need to master.

We are here to help you learn the difference between skimming and scanning and how to properly use these techniques to improve the results in terms of comprehension and information retention of each of your reading sessions.

What is scanning and skimming in reading

Scanning and skimming are reading techniques that involve rapidly passing through a text with quick eye movements and keen attention to keywords and other relevant information. While the two techniques are certainly different, their goals are quite similar and they are both part of the early stages of analytical reading.

Scanning is defined as the process of rapidly looking through a certain text with a clear purpose to identify particular keywords or passages you know you will need to extract important information from.